

CAPABLE

Cancer Patients Better Life Experience

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Exploitation plan and business models –V2

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DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
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CO	Confidential (Consortium members including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified Information (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	

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Versions History

Version	Date	Author	Comments
0.1	13 rd October 2022	UPM	First Table of content
0.2	20 th October 2022	UPM	Description of overall methodology
0.3	5 th November 2022	CAPABLE Consortium	Initial inputs on individual exploitation plan
0.4	12 th November 2022	UPM	Updates on KER1
0.5	19 th November 2022	CAPABLE Consortium	Revision of the overall documents
0.6	26 th November 2022	UPM	Revised version of the exploitation plan
0.7	2 nd December 2022	UPM	Final version of the document
1.0	5 th December 2022		

1. Executive Summary

D8.5 presents the second version of the exploitation plan and business models of the CAPABLE project. During the last 12 months of the project the WP8 focused on the definition of the exploitation strategy of the individual partners and on an overall exploitation of the Overall CAPABLE system. WP8 started strategic alliances and activities to pave the road to the final exploitation activities defining a set of action lines based on the innovation and IPR management, the monitoring of KPI, capacity building for the Consortium, roadmap for commercialization and the stakeholder engagement. The work has been performed in close collaboration with the CAPABLE stakeholder and it has been supported by the Horizon Result booster.

2. Project results

During the first two years of the project WP8 involved the whole CAPABLE consortium to identify the result of the project. The results of these activities have been published in D8.3 that presented an initial joint exploitation strategy and D8.4 that focused on the Intellectual property of the results. During this last year the work focused on two types of results:

- According to the survey presented in D8.4, the partners reported interest in the overall exploitation strategy of the Overall CAPABLE system (named in D8.3 as KER1). The KER1 was deeply discussed within the consortium and refined thanks to the activities of the Horizon Result booster. KER2 (the overall framework of CAPABLE to be reused in other contexts of digital health) and KER3 (the patient's app working in standalone mode) were abandoned at this stage and replaced by the individual results.
- The individual results: WP8 arranged face to face meetings with the partners to discuss the analysis of the perspective of every partner, identify potential results and possible route of exploitation and possible collaboration for joint exploitations.

According to the previous analysis, 3 types of assets have been defined (see D8.3): software, data, and know-how. These ones have been revised, discussed, updated and they are listed in the following three tables:

Table 1: CAPABLE software assets

SW Asset	Short description	Ownership
Overall Capable System (KER1)	The CAPABLE solution is a state-of-the-art digital technology to foster the outpatient management of cancer treatment aimed at patients and their medical team. The patient system is composed of a patient app (Android) and a smartwatch (Asus VivoWatch) that are used to gather physiological and health information (Patient-Reported Experience/Outcome Measures - PREM, PROM) to monitor the health status of the patients during a specific cancer treatment (e.g., immunotherapy). The app provides guidance on how to manage side effects and suggests behavioural modifications to promote the overall wellbeing of the patients, improving their quality of life. The medical team can remotely follow up the health status of the patients and use a clinical decision support system that implements the current clinical guidelines (Computer Interpretable Guidelines) for the management of therapy and side effects; the system also provides prognostic tools to assess the disease trajectory and the treatment response	CAPABLE Consortium
Multimorbidity Controller (GoCom)	The Multimorbidity Controller (GoCom) will receive information from the guidelines after they have completed a run and check for interactions between the guideline recommendations and the patient's existing medications.	UoH
Physician Decision Support Component (Physician DSS / PDSS).	Physician DSS is an adaptor component that interfaces the Deontics Computer Interpretable Guidelines engine to the CAPABLE system.	DEON
Predictive models and tools (risk prediction and disease progression)	Data-driven prediction models that provide an aggregated prediction for patient's outcome given their current state, past history and potential interventions. Also, tools to create the models such as FuseMedML open source and CausalLib open source.	IBM
Natural Language Processing algorithm	This algorithm is used to collect a rich set of patient-related data including unstructured information in the form of text, such as from patients' and caregivers' forums, potentially mails and communication inside the system	UniPV 90%; AIMAC 10%

Virtual Coaching system	The Virtual Coach acts as the "execution environment" for interventions that facilitate and monitor provision of prescribed therapies, increase the motivation and competence of patients and thus improve their engagement in and compliance with these therapies. Interventions are modelled as knowledge-based entities, e.g., formal process models or specifications of "virtual capsules" and are considered separately. VC interacts with other components of the CAPABLE system -- in particular it employs the Deontics Engine to execute clinical guidelines, workflows and rules and it communicates with the patient via the mobile Patient App.	PUT, UoH, UNIPV
Care provider (Clinicians) dashboard	Web app developed to dynamically configure the patient application with the information provided to the patient, and manage patient data by clinicians.	BIT
Patients & caregivers mobile app	Mobile app to allow their disease management, including functionalities such as record their symptoms, management personal data and care plans, receive coaching advice, alerts and recommendations; and communicate with the care providers.	BIT
Ontology-based knowledge-data mapper	The Knowledge-Data Ontology Mapper (KDOM), is a tool that allows mapping different schemas of knowledge and data to each other.	UoH
Data Platform	The CAPABLE data platform aims at storing all the data that are relevant for the project (coming both from the her and generated within the project context). The persistence layer is constituted by an extended version of the OMOP Common Data Model.	BIOM
Case Manager	The Case Manager is the component responsible for driving the reasoning process within the system. The approach adopted by CAPABLE is based on the advertisement of Events: each component hosting a Knowledge Source specifies a set of Events in terms of a combination of facts about the patient.	UNIPV 100%
Knowledge model related to CAPSULE (ontology)	The knowledge model of the capsules related to evidence-based recommendations behind the capsule activity, to its properties related to Fogg's behaviour model, and to representation as FHIR resources	1/3 each for UNIPV, PUT, UH

Table 2: CAPABLE dataset assets

Name of the data set	Description	Ownership
Patient raw dataset	Data already available and extracted from the EHR at the hospitals.	ICSM, NKI
Patients CAPABLE dataset	New data generated by the CAPABLE system. Data collected through questionnaires, wearable or environmental sensors located at the patient home, during the execution of the CAPABLE project.	AMC, ICSM, NKI, BIOMERIS
UX studies data sets	New data generated during the User Experience studies. Data are formed by qualitative and quantitative studies. According to the study protocol and informed consent data are anonymized	UPM, AMC, ICSM, NKI, UNIPV, AIMAC
AIMAC forum data	Data from the AIMAC forum	AIMAC
AIMAC questionnaires data	Data from the AIMAC questionnaires	AIMAC

CAPABLE extended OMOP Datamodel	OMOP CDM is a structure for representing data plus a set of vocabularies to describe them. For CAPABLE scope it has been extended by BIOM	BIOMERIS
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Table 3: CAPABLE know how assets

Partners	Domain	Knowledge description
UNIPV, UoH, DEON, PUT	Computer models	Modelling clinical practice guidelines (CPGs), modelling additional domain knowledge in form of ontological models expressed in the OWL language
AMC, UNIPV, BIOMERIS	Information modelling/system interoperability	Identification and configuration of FHIR resources
UoH, AMC, AIMAC, NKI, ICSM, UPM, UNIPV	System requirements	Identification of unmet clinical needs, Definition of user needs, information needs of cancer patients and oncologists
PUT, UNIPV	Software design and development	Designing complex software systems (e.g., employing multi-agent or actor-model paradigm) and their implementation using modern technologies
BIOMERIS	Data integration	Harmonize separate data sources towards a data model and make them available for secondary use
ICSM, NKI, UNIPV, AMC,	Study design	Definition of study protocols for control cohorts
ICSM, NKI, UNIPV, AMC, UPM	Study design	Definition of study protocols for study cohorts
UPM, ICSM, NKI, UNIPV, AMC	Study design	Definition of study protocols for the user experience evaluation
ICSM, BIOMERIS, NKI, UNIPV	System deployment	Existing environments in the two hospitals
UNIPV, ICSM, NKI, UoH, PUT, DEON, AMC, UPM	System evaluation	Knowledge validation
IBM, PUT	Machine Learning	Developing predictive models for patients' outcomes, application of simulation and machine learning (including reinforced learning) to construct models for

		adjusting wellbeing activity prompts sent to patients
PUT	Wearable sensors	Developing software solutions for communicating with sensors (wearable devices) and dedicated data platforms, processing of data extracted from sensors
UPM, BIT, DEON	Exploitation and business strategy in digital health	Knowledge on market of digital therapeutics in oncology, business models and exploitation strategy
BITSENS	UI & UX design, development and deployment	Improving UX based on advanced prototyping, mobile apps

The next section will detail first the overall exploitation of the Overall Capable system and then it will present the individual exploitation strategy of every partner.

3. Overall Capable system

The section details the exploitation and business plan for the KER1 that refers to the Overall Capable System. During this year the Consortium focused on these specific results and joined the service of the Horizon Result Booster to refine the business plan. This section details the most updated version of the work.

3.1 The problem

Cancer is the leading cause of death for people under 70 years in most of the countries worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million deaths in 2020. Cancer is a complex disease that causes late and long-term side effects due to the malignancy of the condition and the treatment; this reduces the quality of life of the patient and families and generates a significant social and economic burden. In many cases cancer patients receive a treatment (e.g., immunotherapy, chemotherapy) on a day-hospital or home-patient regimen, and it is crucial to accurately follow-up the treatment response, the overall cancer evolution and the patient's side effect. If a patient is having a good evolution, it will have periodic visits from every 2 weeks to every 3 months. The duration of the visit is around 20 minutes, which in some cases is not enough to address all the issues of a patient. The following list of problems has been identified:

PB1 for the hospital: lack of time to spend with each patient.

During the visit, the health professional collects information from the patient and eventually requests additional lab tests to better investigate the health status. In-between two visits, the health professional is not informed on the evolution of the disease and on the possible onset of side effects or signs of deterioration of the health status.

PB2 for the hospital: improving symptom reporting and monitoring.

To better manage the treatment, it is crucial to acknowledge the onset of symptoms and their grade as soon as they appear, and explain to the patient what to do and decide if this can be self-managed by the patient at home, or if it requires further visits and clinical interventions. The classical follow-up model is based on 1) periodic visits, some of which could be not necessary and 2) unscheduled visits, triggered by certain reported symptoms, which often occur too late when the symptom has worsened. The overall knowledge of the disease evolution in outpatient settings is also requested to better understand the treatment response of the patients.

PB 3 for the hospitals: tracking patient status remotely.

In standard care the oncologists have no access to the health status of the patients at home. This information would be crucial to better understand the evolution of the treatment response and side effects, and it would save time during the hospital visits. From the initial focus group with the clinicians, it is also important to track the psycho-social and overall well-being of the home patients.

PB 4 for the hospital: improve adherence of cancer treatment.

The adherence to the treatment is the key for a successful therapy. The hospitals nowadays rely on the patient's feedback during the control visits. There is a need to support home patients to foster their treatment adherence. This also emerged during the initial patient interviews where they admit that they often called clinicians to ask if and how to continue their treatment in presence of side effects. However, patients also mentioned that they experience doctors being too busy, so they delegate nurse practitioners to face those needs, while patients sometimes have the need to talk to the actual treating oncologist indeed. Additionally, there are specific barriers for the adoption of new digital health technology:

PB 5 for the hospital governance it might be hard to teach/convince healthcare professionals to use a new program

The current standard health care organizations are not considering the required additional resources for the use of the telemonitoring services, and the telemedicine-related tasks are not recognized as part of the clinical processes. This is a systematic common barrier in the healthcare system¹; one solution could be to include this in the reimbursement / payment models. There is a need to establish proper specialized units to manage telemedicine systems and properly integrate them in the standard clinical processes.

PB 6: difficulties to integrate new Digital Health Product in the hospital information system.

The hospital information systems are complex and incrementally integrated with other subsystems (PACS², Electronic Health Records, etc) following security and privacy policies that are very strict and conservative to grant the privacy of the patients. This causes barriers to integrate new systems to the Health Care Record of the patients. For this reason, some companies of the Digital Health Market provide also cloud based solutions that manage the information independently from the Hospital Information System.

In the digital market of oncology there are companies that are already providing tools for the diagnostic (based on imaging of genetic data), or support for Electronic Health Records. In case that they would enter in the digital therapeutics market they can face the following problems:

PB 1: for the MedTech companies: Complexity of the cancer treatment domain.

The complexity of the cancer domain depends on the complexity of the disease, of the treatment's options, side effects and the need to harmonize this with the clinical practice guidelines. CAPABLE is focusing on modelling services to support the treatment of the melanoma cancer and renal cell carcinoma as the two main cancer types considered in the project, plus a set of other cancer types, namely breast, lung, thyroid and head&neck cancer.

PB 2 for MedTechs, they focus on hospital needs, now there is a need to create services for patients at home. This is a growing market. The companies would like to increase market share and increase visibility.

3.2 Alternative solutions

There are three alternative solutions:

- Standard Care (NO tele-monitoring system, just phone call to follow-up the patients)
- Competitors (Kaiku Health³, Bioformis⁴ etc), that provide a telemonitoring solution for patients that are following an oncological treatment.
- Patient can decide to find information in the Web and eventually download and pay for an app to have support (e.g., Chemowave⁵). In some hospitals (also in NKI) the doctors recommend downloading an app for self-management of specific symptoms (e.g., UNTIRE⁶).

The following table shows how the alternative solutions solve the problems presented in the previous section.

Table 4: Alternative solutions to CAPABLE

¹<https://www.healthcarevaluehub.org/advocate-resources/publications/telemedicine-decreasing-barriers-and-increasing-access-healthcare>

² Picture Archiving and Communication System

³ <https://kaikuhealth.com/>

⁴ <https://biofourmis.com/>

⁵ <https://chemowave.com/>

⁶ <https://untire.me/>

	Lack of time for visit	Improve symptoms monitoring	Monitor patient health	Improve adherence	Additional workload of digital services
Capable	We expect to reduce visit number and duration	Instant feedback to the patient and request of follow up to the health professional	Collection of PREM/PROM and physiological data using wearable sensor	Digital service to promote the treatment adherence of home-patients, suggestion on how to manage moderate symptoms	CAPABLE will add a workload for nurses. This is minimized by a stratification approach based on alert generation
Standard Care	Visits are the only opportunity to get information from patients. With the pandemic also phone calls have been used to remotely assess patients	This depends on how patients perceive the gravity of the symptom and react to that. Also, it is important that patients remind past symptoms during follow-up visits.	This is possible during the visits.	Health professional can give proper instructions but then this depends on how the patient stick to the recommendation	After the visit routines usually the health professionals update the Electronic Health record
Competitors	The benefit of the remote follow-up is to reduce the visits time and frequency	Symptom's reporting is supported but not all the systems implement the guidelines recommendations	Competitors collect health information. Many just focus on cancer-related information and not on the overall patient wellbeing	Many competitors state that the solution improve adherence	Competitors are not mentioning the added workload for the health professionals
Self-management app	During the visit patients could share the symptom evolution using an app (e.g., Chemowave)	Many apps just support symptom reporting, but no feedback and suggestions are given to the user	No monitoring is possible	The use of a diary might improve the adherence	No additional workload for Health professional

3.3 Competitors analysis update

There is an increased number of competitors. The landscape also improves thanks to the pandemics, since now the healthcare system is more open to telemonitoring solutions. The EU also puts a lot of attention on the cancer pandemic and set up a strategic plan called 'Beat the cancer'. This is also pushing the interest from the healthcare industry in the market. D8.1 and D8.2 presented an initial market analysis that has been periodically updated in a registry of competitors. The repository of the competitor is available here:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Ow6u4zPvcyjoDaM79JoOHQYMXa1ng4b7/edit#gid=1889730072>

From the analysis CAPABLE differentiates from the competitors to be a **comprehensive solution that covers all the functionalities proposed by the competitors and propose an integrated care** approach like the platform Living With that gives access to

different health professionals (nurses, psychologists, dietician), implements the clinical guidelines as other 8 competitors. **No one of the competitors supported specific personalized treatment for kidney or melanoma cancer as CAPABLE does.** Just two competitors support all the types of cancer just because the solution focuses on providing the support to a specific therapy (e.g., chemotherapy) or to a specific side effect like Untire app. There is a clear opportunity for CAPABLE to differentiate for the capacity to support other types of cancer, and in fact a set of patients with other cancer types will be enrolled in one of centers (ICSM). **Artificial intelligence represents another additional opportunity for CAPABLE, the prognostic model will have the advantage to be unique for the target populations.**

3.4 Unique Value Proposition

Our Service helps hospitals that want to improve the efficiency of the visits and overall follow up of cancer patients during the treatment phase.

The CAPABLE service can support the hospitals by providing a tool to monitor symptoms and physiological status in the patient's home, follow the clinical guidelines and provide recommendations to the patients in case of no critical situation and alert the health professionals in case that a specific attention to a patient is required.

In the clinical study we expect to improve the quality of life of the patients by 20-30% and reduce the number of visits in patients that have a good response to the treatment.

3.5 Description of the solution

The CAPABLE solution is a state-of-the-art digital technology to foster the outpatient management of cancer treatment aimed at patients and oncologists. The patient system is composed of a patient app (Android) and a smartwatch (Asus VivoWatch) that are used to gather vital signs and additional health information (Patient reported experience and outcomes - PREM, PROM). The app provides guidance on how to manage side effects and suggests behavioural modifications to promote the overall wellbeing of the patients, improving their quality of life. The oncologists can remotely follow up the health status of the patients and use a clinical decision support system that implements some of the current ESMO clinical guidelines (Computer Interpretable Guidelines) for the management of therapy and side effects; the system also provides prognostic tools to assess the disease trajectory and the treatment response.

3.6 Target Market

The overall digital therapeutics market was in 2018 of 2,24 billion and it is expected to be 9,64 Billion dollars by 2026. This market includes all the digital solutions for wellness and disease management. We consider that the specific cancer market could be 1% worldwide. This sector is not including other specific cancer markets related to diagnostic and medical treatment. The European digital therapeutics market was valued at \$503.48 million in 2018 and is expected to reach \$2,274.03 million by 2026 with a CAGR of 20.6% during the forecast period⁷. We estimate that applications specific for oncology can be around 2-3% of the European market, between 45M€ and 68M€.

Pandemics prompt focus on digital and virtual care and the global digital health market has grown substantially. In a 2020 survey it was estimated that by 2025, 12% of healthcare expenditure would be on digital products and services⁸.

⁷<https://www.marketwatch.com/press-release/europe-digital-therapeutics-market-scope-and-overview-incredible-possibilities-with-growth-prospects-by-2031-progressing-at-a-cagr-of-206-during-the-forecast-period-2022-01-10>

⁸<https://htai.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/210901-HTAi-2021-Panel-Report-Assessment-of-Digital-Health-1.pdf>

In Spain in 2016 there were 210 public 217 private oncology departments, and they represent the 47% of the total hospital infrastructure of the Iberian country⁹. According to a report from 2020 from the Spanish Patient Coalition¹⁰ the cost of cancer is 19,3 M€ / Year, the 48% is represented by direct costs, 12% by indirect medical costs and 40% societal costs (patients, caregivers, productivity loss). The overall costs are estimated being 55% from the National Health System and 45% from patients and families. The average of direct medical costs for treatment of no prevalent cancers (as melanoma and renal cell carcinoma) is around 11,82K€ / patient (data from 2018). The medical follow-up costs are of 29,7K€, the transportation costs of 2K€ patient/year.

3.7 CAPABLE Use Model

The use model is to provide a service in a public or private cloud according to the preferences of the hospitals. The customer will pay a year subscription based on the number of clinical units, health professionals and patients that will use the system. (Standard fee). It is also possible to purchase specific packs with a pre-set number of licenses for health professionals, patients and a specific number of smartwatches, as follow:

1. Small plan license for one clinical centre for 5 health professionals, 25 patients with 25 wearable sensors
2. App plan: license for one clinical centre for 10 health professionals, 50 patients (no sensor is included in the pack)
3. Pro plan: license for one clinical centre for 10 health professionals, 100 patients with 100 wearable sensors

Additionally, the customers will pay a fee for the deployment of the CAPABLE technology in a private cloud inside the hospital infrastructure. The fee will include hardware costs and deployment of the technology service.

The use model will be linked to the following services that will add value and will improve the customer's experience.

- Commercial and financial service to close contracts with the clients. Every customer will be followed by a commercial agent that will follow-up all the pre and post purchase processes.
- Creation of customer support and training service. The new customer will have access to training services to be used to build the technological skills of the health professionals to use the CAPABLE system and train the enrolled patients.
- Additionally, it is possible to purchase specific learning courses for a group of patients in case the hospital cannot afford the training of the patients.
- Deployment and maintenance: these are ancillary services linked to the CAPABLE server. The customer can decide to use the service on a cloud solution or to deploy in the intranet of the target hospital. The service will support the customer to choose the best solutions and will be able to sell to the clients dedicated servers to be used for the intranet option. Service then will include all the activities to set up the CAPABLE service.
- Management of end user devices (sensors, mobiles)- during the purchase of the service the customer will be able to decide to purchase wearable sensors and mobile phones for patients. This use model will purchase the devices to the specific provider and manage the logistic to deliver to the customer.
- It will be possible to offer customers the possibility to integrate CAPABLE in the Hospital Information System or to personalize the app or the services according to specific need.

⁹ https://www.sanidad.gob.es/organizacion/sns/planCalidadSNS/docs/Cancer_EyR.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.contraelcancer.es/sites/default/files/content-file/Informe-Los-costes-cancer.pdf>

3.7 CAPABLE business model

The business model presents the details on how an organization or a Consortium of organizations (including project partners, third party business partners, value-added service providers etc.) creates, delivers, and generates value from the CAPABLE results. The Exploitation and Business Model approach used in WP8 is based on Business Model Generation – “Canvas”, a management tool that is used to design business models. The traditional Canvas model has been filled to draft the CAPABLE business model of the KER1. All the elements of the Canvas model have been previously described in these deliverable sections, and it is presented in figure 1:

Figure 1: The CAPABLE business model for KER1

3.8 Pricing of the solution

The CAPABLE digital service will be based on a subscription model similarly to other solutions like Living With¹¹ (A telemonitoring solution from UK)

We consider different revenues that will come from different types of purchase from the hospitals.

Standard fee: the hospital will be able to select the proper volume of clinicians and patients and decide how many wearable devices to purchase. The fee will be the following:

- Start-up fee :3000€ Access to clinical dashboard (50€ professional / month)
- Patient account to use the APP (15€ patient /month)
- Wearable sensors 200€/ patient

The hospital can alternatively buy the following packs:

- Small Plan: CAPABLE for 5 health care professionals and 25 patient apps with wearable sensors:14000 € / year
- App plan CAPABLE for 10 health care professionals and 50 patient apps (NO wearable sensors) 16000 € / year
- Pro plan CAPABLE for 10 health care professionals and 100 patient apps and 100 wearable sensors

In case that a hospital makes a contract (that requires a standard fee or pack purchase) it will be possible to:

- Integrate CAPABLE with the Hospital Information System (between 5000 to 15000€)
- Install CAPABLE in a local server in the hospital (7000€ that will include the Server hardware)
- Personalize the App of the CAPABLE service (2000€ - 20000€)

3.9 Early adopters

We consider as best early adopters private hospitals that already have in place telemonitoring services for patients based on phone calls and videoconferences. This has been implanted in many hospitals during the pandemic and should mitigate the organizational barriers to use new digital technology. Another activity that is planned for the next period is a survey among hospital managers to understand the situation across different hospitals in Italy, Spain, and Poland. This will help us to better identify early adopters. At this stage there are few cases in Europe of hospitals using a service like CAPABLE.

3.10 Exploitation plan for KER1

The exploitation of the overall CAPABLE system could be done in two phases:

- **Evidence phase:** at this stage the system will be refined and optimized. The system will be also validated in a large Randomized Clinical Trial to proof the effectiveness. The results of this phase will set the basis to get the Medical Certification. This phase will have a duration of 1,5 / 2 years. The phase 1 will allow to grow from TRL6 (as stated in the grant agreement) to TRL8.
- **Business phase:** during this phase the commercial activities will start. A company will provide the maintenance and improvement of the service and the customer relationships.

3.11 Impact of KER1

The impact will be the improvement of the QoL of patients that undergo cancer therapy (e.g., immunotherapy, chemotherapy), better use of resources in the oncological clinical units, early intervention to manage the side effects that may impact the overall evolution of the treatment response. The KER1 will also contribute to the impact of the call SC1-DTH-01-2019 in the following areas:

¹¹ <https://www.livingwith.health/>

- Emerging data driven analytics and advanced simulation methods to study causal mechanisms and improve forecasts of health outcomes, identification of disease trajectories and relapse; (KPI: number of deployed solutions, number of patients and health professionals using the solutions)
- Better and faster means of high-quality response to prevent or timely address development of new medical conditions and/or improve the quality of life; (KPI: number of early reported side effects)
- Better knowledge for improved patient counselling as well as to improve follow-up of patients; (KPI: improved knowledge of patients on cancer management)
- Novel information on health maintenance, onset and course of medical conditions with a view to optimize prevention and treatment; (KPI: number of deployed solutions and number of patients using CAPABLE)
- Improved quality of life after cancer treatment, strengthening personal confidence and enhancing employability; (KPI: QoL improvement according to the expected results of the clinical study of year 2023)

Other societal impacts will be:

- Job created: 1 new Company with 2-3 employers fully dedicated
- Turnover of 1-2M€ /year

4. Individual exploitation plans

The following section details the individual exploitation plan of all the members of the CAPABLE Consortium.

Università Degli Studi Di Pavia (UNIPV)

UNIPV is planning to exploit the CAPABLE results and to implement a plan to improve the research and education activities in different interconnected tracks.

The first one will consist of exploiting an individual result, i.e. the software tool "Case Manager" that has been conceived as a general service, to be reused in other e-health projects to orchestrate clinical services. The plan is to analyse how to adapt the Case Manager in order to be used in other complex systems, similar to CAPABLE, and how to exploit it by re-using the component developed by UNIPV. Another exploitation action will consist of supporting the re-use of the overall CAPABLE telemonitoring system (KER1), of adapting it to systematically collect PREM and PROM measures to be further used in research studies, and to advance on clinical guidelines modelling and on the creation of a Clinical Decision Support System. A plan for the further exploitation of CAPABLE will be to look for national or European research funds to execute a multicentre study with a higher number of patients. This study will demonstrate the clinical benefits of the telemonitoring solution and also, possibly, allow the testing of new types of sensors (e.g., environmental sensors and personal medical devices) that can be used during the remote follow up of cancer patients under treatment, with the purpose of understanding the impact of such novel factors on the clinical status of the patient. At the moment CAPABLE exploits an ancillary app suggesting the best path for a walk, exploiting air pollution sensors located in Pavia. The plan is to integrate this (and other similar) functionalities in a unique application, and extending to other geographical areas.

UNIPV is also interested in exploiting the research result of the project in a number of academic courses (undergraduate courses, Master, Doctorate) in the area of Computer Informatics and Bio-engineering. In this context, UNIPV is also interested in using the results from DEONTICS for education purposes, to simulate different clinical scenarios to MD students. The plan is to use the knowledge gained during the CAPABLE project to create advanced AI courses focused on knowledge modelling and representation that can also be available to medical students. This exploitation will be supported by the Knowledge Transfer Office of the University.

Finally, the generated knowledge will be disseminated in different conferences and scientific publications.

University of Haifa (UoH)

One relevant result of UoH is the Knowledge Data Ontology Mapper ("New-KDOM") that can operate as an independent component that can define clinical abstractions and query them based on raw data. The assumption is that raw data is stored in a data repository that uses the HL7 FHIR standard. New-KDOM defines new mapping classes and operators that support hierarchical and temporal mappings and allows operating with uncertainty. Modelers can define abstractions by specifying the mapping instances using an XML KDOM Editor and the runtime component of KDOM generates and executes the FHIR queries. KDOM can accept requests from a generic system component to get an abstraction and can return the results as FHIR resources (Observation, Medication Request, Communication).

UoH will explore how to apply KDOM beyond the setting of the CAPABLE DSS in clinical settings, leveraging on the network of hospitals in Europe and Israel.

This process will involve our young researchers who may want to be more involved in the commercialization of their components (New-KDOM, GoCom).

Finally the generated knowledge during the course of CAPABLE project will be exploited in (a) publishing and sharing the novel methods that has been developed, (b) generating a

portfolio describing future research ideas that builds on CAPABLE existing research, (c) delivering talks and including this knowledge in courses.

Biomeris Srl

BIOMERIS is specialized in implementing and personalizing software solutions for integrating, exploring and analysing heterogeneous patient data sources. The partner will leverage on individual results, the CAPABLE data platform that will be made publicly available in the OMOP community¹². This will increase the visibility of the BIOMERIS services and expertise. In parallel BIOMERIS will be also available to support the further exploitation of the overall CAPABLE system (KER1) and support the deployment and maintenance of the system once this has been industrialized and optimized for commercial use. The partner will be also available to disseminate and promote the CAPABLE overall solution to the network of hospitals that BIOMERIS serves for the data management activities.

Academisch Medisch Centrum Bij De Universiteit Van Amsterdam (AMC)

AMC will take profit of the results of CAPABLE to strengthen the knowledge in different technological areas as 1) Guideline modelling 2) FAIRification approaches and methods 3) healthcare Interoperability and customization (with a special focus on OMOP and FHIR) 4) Medical device certification 5) Modelling clinical needs and the patient user experience.

This knowledge will be used in different business contexts

- 1) Academic: the assets will be integrated in medical informatics training courses at Bachelor and Master level
- 2) Research: the knowledge will be used in other projects related to the implementation and/or customization of specific healthcare information standards
- 3) Consultancy: AMC will collaborate with companies and hospitals to support the implementation of interoperable solutions in healthcare
- 4) Policy making: AMC will be involved in discussions with research funding organizations and government to develop policies towards actual implementation of FAIR approaches and a more rigorous approach towards interoperability.

AMC will also support the promotion of KER1 and the dissemination of the overall Capable system leveraging on the local Network of stakeholders in digital health, e.g., in matchmaking events, digital health technologies conferences, or as a demonstrator in the annual Smart Health Care Relay event¹³.

IBM Israel - Science And Technology Ltd

The results produced by IBM in the CAPABLE projects are the Predictive models and tools (risk prediction and disease progression) and the consequent improved knowledge in Machine Learning. These results will be exploited with three strategic actions that are in line with the company roadmap.

- 1) Enhancing IBM platform for accelerated discovery. This platform is based on IBM hybrid cloud, AI, and quantum computing.
- 2) Contribute to open source that IBM published in the BiomedSciAI organization, such as FuseMedML¹⁴. FuseMedML is an open-source python-based framework designed to enhance collaboration and accelerate discoveries in Fused Medical data through advanced Machine Learning technologies. Initial version is PyTorch-based and focuses on deep learning on medical imaging and digital pathology.
- 3) Participation in AI competitions e.g., BMMR2 in breast cancer, KiTS 21 in kidney cancer. Also, organization of challenges e.g. Knight challenge in kidney cancer¹⁵.

Additionally, IBM will leverage the insights from capable predictive models to engage companies and hospitals in new research projects such as the engagement with Cleveland

¹² <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

¹³ <https://slimmezorgestafette.nl/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/BiomedSciAI/fuse-med-ml>

¹⁵ <https://research.ibm.com/haifa/Workshops/KNIGHT/>

Clinic. There is also a collaboration with DEONTICS to support the use of the AI models in the guidelines modelling process. Finally, IBM is also interested in supporting the uptake of the Overall Capable System (KER1), and to use new incoming data from patients to generalize and improve the models.

Bitsens Jsc

BITSENS will leverage on the technical results of the development of WP6 interfaces to launch a new product in the wellness market for symptom reporting. This app will operate in standalone mode without the link with specific health professionals and no clinical decisions and recommendations will be provided. The app would be rather used for self-management and tracking purposes. This application will use a classic B2C model in which Bitsens have experience with as well as track record. This seems to be a natural development step for the company. On the other hand Bitsens will also support the exploitation of the overall CAPABLE system, if a suitable legal/operational setup will be created by the consortium (or part of it) where each partner supports their own components. The CAPABLE exploitation will be an opportunity to enter the healthcare market with a B2B solution, and will be a significant leap forward in the company. Because B2B is a more ambitious model, Bitsens will have to secure the resources needs to be invested in market penetration.

Politechnika Poznanska (PUT)

PUT plans to take advantage of both the specific and overall project results.

- The *specific results* include the Virtual Coach component, formal models of patient-oriented clinical guidelines, rules, and workflows, and methods to simulate patients and to predict the most appropriate behaviour change interventions. The methods and models will be used to foster further research on knowledge- and data-driven patient decision support and coaching. Moreover, Virtual Coach together with an additional visualization layer will be used as a testbed and demonstrator of new coaching strategies and methods. This will facilitate the demonstration of results and cooperation with clinical partners from different fields and specialties.
- The overall result (KER1) includes the entire CAPABLE system. The system will be presented as an example of a comprehensive decision-support environment based on modern technology (e.g., wearables) and sound clinical evidence. Moreover, PUT will promote the reuse of the system in other contexts (e.g., in psychology) and together with clinical partners (e.g., medical universities, hospitals, clinics) will look for opportunities for extending the system and for testing in (limited) real-life settings.

The knowledge and experience gained when developing the results discussed above will be shared in different courses offered at PUT to undergraduate and graduate students. Examples of such courses include “Medical informatics” and “AI in biomedical informatics”. Moreover, they will be disseminated at meetings organized by professional associations and societies (e.g., Polish Telemedicine and e-Health Society or the Polish Society of AI in Medicine), and at scientific conferences, seminars, and workshops. PUT will also disseminate the results in other EU projects and initiatives where it participates, and present them to med-tech or pharma companies it cooperates with. Finally, PUT will look for opportunities of deploying the CAPABLE system (or its selected components) in cooperating hospitals in Poznan that provide care to cancer patients.

Istituti Clinici Scientifici Maugeri (ICSM)

The exploitation strategy of ICSM for the CAPABLE project would be to support the maturation of the overall CAPABLE solution. The hospital is interested in consolidating a telemonitoring service for cancer patients and could contribute with the specification, tests and validation of the novel services that can be provided as result of the CAPABLE

exploitation. ICSM has an internal network of hospitals across Italy in which CAPABLE could be promoted and tested.

Stichting Het Nederlands Kanker Instituut-Antoni Van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NKI)

The NKI has an interest in continuing research into telemonitoring services for cancer patients. If the app shows positive results in the pilot study (i.e., clinical benefits for patients and good usability for patients and clinicians), it is anticipated that we can work with clinicians to further test the system in a larger (possibly randomized) study. To that end, we will interview patients and clinicians at the end of the pilot study to assess their willingness to use the app in future practice. Other commercially available apps are currently being used in the NKI. Thus, evaluation of the use of the CAPABLE app will logically be weighed against the experience and cost of these commercial apps. If patients and physicians show interest in using the app in future practice, we as NKI can write a follow-up grant application to set up a multicentre clinical trial to demonstrate the (cost-)effectiveness of the CAPABLE digital intervention. In that case, the NKI would also be interested in being a national reference for the application of new digital services and solutions like CAPABLE and to promote the system in the network of hospitals and patient communities (i.e. matchmaking events, conferences and scientific publications).

Deontics Limited

Deontics sees commercialisation of results as key to our involvement in the CAPABLE project. We pursue two general approaches to deployment of our clinical AI system:

- Backend only, where deontics provides a clinical AI engine hosted in the cloud and accessed via APIs which can be used to integrate the engine into all kinds of systems (the approach taken in CAPABLE);
- Full system, where we provide a web-based UI and integration functionality alongside the engine.

We see KER-1 as an excellent example of the former type of deployment where Deontics can provide the back-end AI and decision support engine. Deontics sees CAPABLE and KER-1 in particular as providing several commercial opportunities:

1. An opportunity to raise the profile of the Deontics system through demonstrations and deployments of the full-scale system in prestigious healthcare organisations.
2. An opportunity to work commercially with CAPABLE partners who can provide front-end, user-facing and system integration skills.
3. A sales opportunity through the direct commercialisation of KER-1.

Deontics can offer dissemination to a network of stakeholders who may be interested in features of the full KER-1 system. For example, stakeholders who wish to improve recruitment of patients to clinical trials. This is seen in part as impacted by difficulties in managing participant wellbeing and side-effects, aspects in which CAPABLE can bring expertise.

Associazione Italiana Malati Di Cancro, Parenti E Amici

AIMAC is interested in promoting the patient's empowerment through the use of the digital solution in healthcare. The CAPABLE solution is attractive because it could be used to improve the quality of the care in clinical settings: for that the partner can support the promotion of the solution throughout FAVO and Aimac's Info Points within the major Italian Hospital. The potential adoption of the CAPABLE solution would also benefit societal studies oriented to identify barriers and gaps for the implementation of digital solutions in healthcare. Moreover, exploiting Aimac's Network, CAPABLE will be introduced and linked to the Joint Action on European Network of expertise¹⁶ in which Aimac and FAVO are already involved. More in specific Aimac will introduce the CAPABLE Project in the Transversal Task Force 3 which is taking into consideration the involvement of IT & AI

¹⁶ EU4H-2021-JA-04: Direct grants to Member States' authorities: network of Comprehensive Cancer Centres: Establishment of new EU Network of Expertise on Cancers and Cancer Conditions (AWP Ref.: DP/C-g-10.1.3)

tools. In providing this network and creating a more tailored one, sustainability of the project concept will be ensured. In parallel AIMAC would also support to have a patient app, not connected to the oncology department (KER3) that could work independently to support the self-management and the counselling.

Universidad Politecnica De Madrid

Thank to be CAPABLE contributions UPM deepen the experience in the design and assessment of personalized health solution in the field of oncology. These results will be exploited with publication in scientific journals and participation in international conferences. The knowledge will be also shared in different Master, Grade and PhD courses in the field of bioengineering and human factors with technology. The exploitation and business activities led by UPM represent a relevant opportunity to position the institution as catalyst of innovation and promoter of novel solutions in the market.

The partner will support the dissemination, and exploitation of the KER1 (The overall Capable system), leading the activities of WP8 but also UPM will be actively involved in finding new opportunities leveraging on the large network of contacts in the healthcare sectors, the participation in the EIT health program and other European Initiative (e.g., EIP on AHA), task forces and joint actions. UPM is also interested to leverage on the CAPABLE results to strengthen the European network of research around cancer, UPM is fully supporting the cluster of projects called "Cancer Survivorship Artificial Intelligence for Wellbeing" and working in close collaboration with patient association as AIMAC, the Spanish GEPAC, the European ECPC to further explore user needs and technology gaps.

5. Overall exploitation plans

This roadmap presents different actions that will be performed in the next period to capitalize and maximize the project’s results. During the current period WP8 focused on creating the pre-condition that, as presented before, focuses on the potential exploitation of individual results and the exploitation of the overall Capable system. The purpose of formulating this Plan is to create the foundation for the joint (consortium-wide) and individual (partner’s) Business Strategies and guide the commercial and non-commercial exploitation paths to ensure the acceptance of market players and stakeholders and the economic sustainability of project’s tangible results. The exploitation plan will focus on a set of actions that will be performed in the last year of the project and it will be based on six action pillars (Figure 2) that are described in the next subsections.

Figure 2: Core elements of the CAPABLE exploitation plan

5.1 Innovation management

The management of innovation is not a simple task, and it requires a very close collaboration between all the stakeholders involved in the process. As presented in D8.2, and illustrated in Figure 3, CAPABLE applies the CEHERES approach¹⁷. At this stage of the project, CAPABLE is close to start the clinical study and this will be an opportunity to start the operationalization process. CAPABLE technology will be launched in two hospitals (ICSM and NKI) and all the novel clinical and non-clinical processes will be tested and evaluated. Thanks to those experimental activities, it will be possible to assess different aspects related to a qualitative analysis about the real-world experience on how the new technology can improve both health professional and patients’s experience and quality of life. The process will also explore how the new technology is perceived, analysing barriers and facilitators to adopt it, exploring the reason behind certain behaviours. This will lead to develop guidance for the adoption of this kind of technology, and the value specification will be refined and adjusted according to market needs and trends.

Figure 3: The CeHRes roadmap¹⁷

5.2 IPR management

D8.3 presented the IPR strategy of the project and presented the IPR registry with three types of assets: software, data and expertise. The IPR Table has been revised every 6 months by the partners. Some little updates have been performed in the software and data asset tables and new knowledge have been reported in the expertise asset sections.

At this stage of the project WP8 defined IPR ownerships and access rights of the results and in the next period the work will focus on the result’s valorisation according to the joint and individual exploitation plans presented at the beginning of this document.

¹⁷ <https://www.utwente.nl/en/bms/ehealth/cehres-roadmap-toolkit/>

Figure 4: Phases of the IP management

The IP procedures (Figure 4) will continue keeping updated the repository of IPR at the following URL

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1rqEX1bpSVL1xvImwx8hMYZH2LwIarHY	b0NoefjwoeE/edit#gid=328286524
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Furthermore, other activities will be the management of the risk related to IPR (the risks presented in D8.3 are still valid), continuing the market surveillance and elaborating procedure for the IP enforcement.

5.3 Monitoring of KPI

Wp8 defined a list of KPI (Key Performance Indicators) to be monitored to assess the overall impact of CAPABLE and its potential innovation. This variable will be used to better specify the value proposition of the project result.

The first group of KPIs includes the overall performances of the CAPABLE system and its impact in the real world.

- **Efficacy indicators:** Quality of life scores of patients (primary endpoint) and caregivers; Number of re-hospitalizations during the follow-up; Number of early detected adverse events; Number of early detected relapses or disease progression; Patient engagement scale.
- **Process outcomes indicators:** Physicians' compliance to the physician's DSS recommendations; Patients' compliance to the coaching system recommendations;
- **System usability/acceptability indicators:** usability/acceptability questionnaires scores.
- **Predictive model performances** and quality of the provided decision support system from the health professionals
- **Use of health resources** of the health professionals and patients involved in the clinical study.

The second group of KPIs will include quantitative information related to the exploitation activities

- Stakeholder engagement and interests: this group of KPI strive depends on the dissemination activities of the project proposed by WP9 that potentially can generate impact for the exploitation activities in terms of:
- Number of exploitation events

- Number of patients that requested to use CAPABLE outside the clinical study
- Number of Health professionals that requested further information and access
- Number of decision makers engaged of interested in the CAPABLE results
- Number of Medtech interested in CAPABLE

For the specific KER1 (the Overall CAPABLE system the following KPIs have been defined:

- KPI1: duration of the visit (20min follow up, 30 min first visit).
- KPI2: side effects of patients during cancer treatment.
- KPI3: time used spent by the health professionals (nurses and oncologists) using the CAPABLE system.
- KPI4: information gathered by CAPABLE that impact the clinical process. The monitoring data can be used to extract the health status and the treatment response of the pharmacological therapy. This information can generate new clinical workflows
- KPI4: Quality of Life of the patient.
- KPI5: level of acceptance of the solution from clinicians

5.4 Capacity building

WP8 supports the partners of the CONSORTIUM to build capacities to exploit the results of the project. These capacities are around 5 pillars:

- Business model: during February and March 2022 the Consortium joined seminars related to business model development provided by IDEARE in the frame of the horizon Results booster Activities.
- Portfolio: WP9 was involved in the activities of Horizon Result Booster and a project portfolio has been created in collaboration with other 3 sister projects (ASCAPE¹⁸, FAITH¹⁹ and BD4QoL²⁰).
- Elevator Pitch: in the last year of the project (2022-2023) WP8 will arrange a set of workshops to support the preparation of elevator pitch to describe the results in a quick, efficient, and clear way to different types of audits (target users, potential buyers).
- Exploitation workshops: during the current period the activities focused on the exploitation strategy of KER1 and on the individual exploitation plan. The next year of the project WP8 will arrange 2 exploitation workshops to agree the final exploitation strategy of the project and to support joint and individual actions on exploitation.
- IPR workshops: the next year will be dedicated to raise awareness in the Consortium on way to protect the results and licensing schemas for joint or 3rd party collaboration.

5.5 Roadmap to commercialization

As previously described in section 3.10 *Exploitation plan for KER1*, the exploitation of the overall CAPABLE solution will need first efforts for the certification of the system as a Medical Device. For that WP8 will work in the next year on two activities:

- Integrate the Health Technologies Assessment activities in the final study protocol- During the 2021-2022 WP8 contributed to WP7 activities providing support to define goals and objectives of the Health Technology Assessment study. This cooperation work will make possible the overall assessment

¹⁸ <https://www.ascap-project.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.h2020-faith.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.bd4qol.eu/>

activities (Task 8.4 Pre-market health technology assessment) that will start at month 42.

- Support to standardization and certification in the last year of the project- WP8 will support the Consortium to the implementation of the directive for Medical Device Regulation and the next coming Artificial Intelligence act (that now is at proposal stage). WP8 will support the organization of seminars, twinning activities with other projects to discuss best practices, barriers and set up with the consortium an action plan to follow the EU legal frameworks for the commercialization of the CAPABLE results.

5.6 Stakeholder engagement

This year WP8 started dissemination and engagement activities to increase the collaborations of the CAPABLE consortium and maximize the dissemination level of the project results. Thanks to the collaboration network of UPM it was possible to join the cluster called "Cancer Survivorship Artificial Intelligence for Wellbeing"²¹. The initiative was launched by FAITH¹⁹ project and aims to start a close collaboration with other projects to share the experience and engage external stakeholders and end-users to obtain their views, and to verify and validate the ongoing work of the engaging projects. To this end, a series of "Meetings of Minds" has been organised, which WP8 joined as representative of CAPABLE project.

Another relevant activity was the beginning of a collaboration of a network of patient associations: thank to the support of AIMAC partner it was possible to start discussion with the Spanish GEPAC²² (an umbrella organization of cancer association) and ECPC (The European Cancer Patient Coalition)²³.

The plan of the next year will be to continue the activities with the patient associations and with the cluster "Cancer Survivorship Artificial Intelligence for Wellbeing" and to present the results to relevant stakeholder of the healthcare sectors as hospital managers, innovation networks (e.g. EIT health), investors in the field of health care. This will be possible thank to the results of the clinical study that will provide deeper insights on the benefits and impact of the CAPABLE solution.

²¹ <https://www.h2020-faith.eu/tag/cs-aiw-cluster/>

²² <http://www.gepac.es/>

²³ <https://ecpc.org/>

6. Conclusions

The presented work set up the basis for the last year's exploitation activities. Three main outcomes have been generated:

- 1) Exploitation and business plan for the overall CAPABLE system named as KER1.
- 2) The individual exploitation plans.
- 3) The roadmap for the overall exploitation plan.

The next year the roadmap will be implemented and merged with the CAPABLE finalization activities (mostly related with the execution of the pilots, the analysis of the results and the dissemination of the results).

The performed work required high level of involvement of the CAPABLE consortium: it was challenging to set up close collaboration actions to identify the results, draft the exploitation strategy of business plan and discuss all the individual exploitation intentions.